

Scheme 1

latter on condensation with malonic acid in the presence of dry pyridine afforded (*E*)-2-undecen-1,11-dioic acid **4**, which was esterified with dry methanol containing catalytic amount of $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ to obtain diester **5**. This on treatment with hydrazinehydrate in methanol at steam bath temperature yielded dihydrazide **6**. Condensation of methanolic solution of dihydrazide with phenylisothiocyanate at steam bath temperature afforded thiocarbamate **7**. Treatment of **7** with ice-cold conc. H_2SO_4 at room temperature for 2 h gave bis-thiadiazole **8**, while, **7** in 4 (*N*) NaOH when heated under reflux in methanol and I_2 in KI solution yielded bis-oxadiazole **9** as outlined in Scheme 1. The compounds were tested for their biological activity.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infra red spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR on Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer. The purity of all the compounds was routinely checked by TLC.

9-Oxononanoic acid (**3**) :

A solution of pot. periodate (7.5 g) in 1 *N* H_2SO_4 (375 ml) was added rapidly to a vigorously stirred solution of *threo*-aleuritic acid (10.0 g) in $\text{MeOH-H}_2\text{O}$ solution (250 ml : 250 ml, v/v) at 40 °C. After 10 min the reaction mixture was cooled to 15 °C in a methanol-ice

bath and extracted with ether (2 × 500 ml). The organic layer was extracted with saturated NaHCO_3 solution (250 ml) and the combined aqueous layers were acidified with conc. HCl and following the procedure reported in literature⁹ yielded **3** (6.2 g) as a viscous liquid, which was purified over a column of neutral alumina using ether as eluent; ν_{max} 2926, 2855 ($-\text{CH}_2$), 1728 ($-\text{CHO}$), 1700 cm^{-1} ($-\text{COOH}$); ^1H NMR : 1.11–1.81 (10H, m, CH_2COOH), 2.32 (4H, t, CH_2CHO), 9.56 (1H, t, CHO), 9.85 (1H, bs, COOH) (Found : C, 62.7; H, 9.3. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$: C, 62.8; H, 9.3%).

(*E*)-2-Undecen-1,11-dioic acid (**4**) :

Compound **3** (3.0 g) dissolved in dry pyridine (15 ml) and malonic acid (3.0 g) was added to it and the reaction mixture heated on steam bath till effervescence of CO_2 ceased. It was then poured into ice-cold water. The mixture was then extracted with ether. Etheral layer was washed with 10% HCl solution followed by water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent afforded **4** as a solid (2.5 g), which was crystallized from ethyl acetate, m.p. 97–99 °C; IR (KBr) : 2930, 2860 ($-\text{CH}_2$), 1700

(*E*)

($-\text{COOH}$), 970 cm^{-1} ($\text{CH}=\text{CH}$); ^1H NMR : 1.12–1.82 (8H, m, $-\text{CH}_2$), 5.25 (2H, t, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$), 9.87 (1H, bs, $-\text{COOH}$) (Found : C, 61.7; H, 8.3. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 61.7; H, 8.4%).

Dimethyl (*E*)-2-undecen-1,11-dioate (**5**) :

Unsaturated dioic acid **4** (2.2 g) was heated with dry MeOH containing catalytic amount of $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ on a steam bath for 15 min. It was then cooled and poured into ice-water and reaction mixture was extracted with ether. Etheral layer was washed with 5% Na_2CO_3 solution to remove excess of $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ followed by water, dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of ether gave **5** (2.0 g) as a liquid, which was purified by column chromatography with neutral alumina with ether as eluent; ν_{max} 2920 ($-\text{CH}_2$),

(*E*)

1730 ($-\text{COOCH}_3$), 968 cm^{-1} ($\text{CH}=\text{CH}$); ^1H NMR : 3.65 (3H, t, COOCH_3), 5.29 (2H, m, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$) (Found : C, 64.4; H, 8.9. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 64.5; H, 9.0%).

(*E*)-2-Undecen-1,11-dioic acid dihydrazide (**6**) :

A mixture of dimethyl (*E*)-2-undecen-1,11-dioate (50 mmol), hydrazine hydrate (100 mmol), dry MeOH (25 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled

to room temperature. The dihydrazide that separated was filtered, dried and crystallized from methanol, m.p. 187–189 °C, yield 59%; IR (KBr) : 3325 and 3270 (NH₂/NH), 2936 (CH₂), 1682 (C=O), 970 cm⁻¹ (CH=CH); ¹H NMR : 8.90 (1H, s, -CONH), 4.15 (2H, s, NH₂), 2.57–1.42 (14H, m, 7CH₂), 5.28 (2H, m, CH=CH) (Found : C, 54.4; H, 9.8; N, 23.0. C₁₁H₂₂O₂N₂ requires : C, 54.5; H, 9.9; N, 23.1%).

Thiocarbamate (7) :

Methanolic solution of **6** (0.01 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.21 mol) was refluxed for 4 h. It was then cooled to yield a solid, which was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from ethyl acetate, yield 76%, m.p. 91–92 °C; IR (KBr) : 3225–3265 (NH), 2912 (C–H), 1680–1685 (secondary -CONH), 1220 (C=S), 968 cm⁻¹ (C=CH₂); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : 3.22 (1H, s, OH-CH₂), 9.32 (2H, t, OH-CH₂), 7.12–7.41 (5H, m, C₆H₅), 9.6 (2H, s, NH), 9.8 (1H, s, NH), 5.25 (2H, m, C=CH₂) (Found : C, 58.2; H, 6.1; N, 16.3; S, 12.4. C₂₅H₃₂O₂N₆S₂ requires : C, 58.5; H, 6.2; N, 16.4; S, 12.5%).

Bis-thiadiazole (8) :

The above thiocarbamate (0.48 g) was added in portion to cold conc. H₂SO₄ (7 ml) with stirring at 0 °C. The temperature was maintained for 1 h and then the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The contents were warmed to 50 °C, cooled and poured into crushed ice. Sodium bicarbonate was added to neutralize the acid partially. The solid separated was filtered, washed with water, dried, crystallized from MeOH, m.p. 160–161 °C, yield 60%; IR (KBr) : 3320–3300 (secondary -NH), 3005 (C–H), 1500–1600 (conjugated cycle system C=N), 1175–1170 cm⁻¹ (C=S); ¹H NMR (DMSO) : 2 doublets at 6.9 and 7.8 corresponding to protons, 6.5–7.8 (4H, d, Ar-H), 1.1–2.8 (16H, m, 8-CH₂), 5.2 (2H, m, C=CH₂) (Found : C, 62.8; H, 5.7; N, 17.5; S, 13.3. C₂₅H₂₈N₆S₂ requires : C, 62.9; H, 5.8; N, 17.6; S, 13.4%).

Bis-oxadiazole (9) :

Sodium hydroxide (4 N, 2 ml) was added with stirring to the suspension of thiocarbamate **7** (0.49 g) in methanol (25 ml) under the chilled condition. Iodine 5% in KI solution was added gradually to the resulting clear solution with stirring till a permanent yellow colour persisted.

The reaction mixture was heated under reflux with the addition of more I₂ solution till a permanent iodine colour is attained. Excess of methanol was distilled off and the contents were poured into ice-cold water.

The solid separated was filtered, washed with 0.1% Na₂S₂O₃ solution and water, dried and crystallized from MeOH, m.p. 240–242 °C, yield 50%; IR (KBr) : 2880 (CH₂), 3150–3100 (-NH), 1510–1500 (C=N), 1175–1170 (C=S), 1187 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C); ¹H NMR (DMSO) : 11.15 (2H, s, OH), 7.8 (4H, d, Ar-H), 6.91 (4H, d, Ar-H), 1.12–2.90 (16H, m, 8-CH₂), 1.35 (2H, s, SH), 5.23 (2H, m, C=CH₂) (Found : C, 47.7; H, 5.5; N, 17.1; S, 19.5. C₁₃H₁₈O₂N₄S₂ requires : C, 47.8; H, 5.5; N, 17.2; S, 19.6%).

Biological activities :

Anthelmintic activity :

Anthelmintic activity of dihydrazide **6** was performed by standard method¹⁰ on earthworm. Preliminary experiment showed compound to possess anthelmintic activity.

Anticonvulsant activity :

The anticonvulsant activity of thiocarbamate **7** was performed against pentylenetetrazole induced convulsion in mice by the literature method¹¹. The compound at a dose of 10 mg/kg bodyweight showed anticonvulsant activity. The compound do not abolish pentylene induced convulsion where as the diazepam, the standard drug abolished the convulsion.

Antibacterial activity :

The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity according to cup-plate method¹². The zone of inhibition was recorded after 24 h at 37 °C.

Antibacterial activity of compound 6 :

The compound was moderate sensitive to *Vibrio cholerae* 1313 and *Vibrio cholerae* 1315, MIC was found to be 50 µg/ml (±, inhibited growth) (0*-control DMSO).

Maximum active against *E. coli* ETEC LTS7 and *Escherichia coli* ATCC 10536, MIC was found to be 25 µg/ml. Maximum active against *Shigella dysenteriae* **2** and *Shigella dysenteriae* **9** where MIC was found to be 25 µg/ml.

Antibacterial activity of compound 7 :

The compound was maximum active against *E. coli*

ETEC LTS7 and *Escherichia coli* ATCC 10536 where MIC was found to be 25 µg/ml (±, inhibited growth). Moderate sensitive against *Vibrio cholerae* 1313 and *Vibrio cholerae* 1315, *Shigella dysenteriae* 2 and *Shigella dysenteriae* 9 where MIC was found to be 25 µg/ml (±).

Antibacterial activity of compound 8 :

It was found to be maximum active against *Vibrio cholerae* 1313 (MIC 100 µg/ml) and *Vibrio cholerae* 1315 (MIC 25 µg/ml, ±).

Moderate sensitive to *Shigella dysenteriae* 2 and *Shigella dysenteriae* 9 (MIC 50 µg/ml, ±).

Antibacterial activity of compound 9 :

The titled compound was maximum active against *Vibrio cholerae* 1313 and *Vibrio cholerae* 1315, *E. coli* ETEC LTS7, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 10536 and *S. boydii* B 22461 (MIC 50 µg/ml, ±), where ± indicated inhibited growth.

All the tested compounds showed comparable activity with ciprofloxacin used as standard drug.

Antifungal activity :

The compound 6 was tested for its antifungal activity against *C. albicans* ATCC 10231, at varying MIC values by filter paper disc technique¹³. Clotrimazole was used as the standard antifungal agent. The tested compound showed inhibition at 200 µg/ml. The standard showed marked activity at 300 µg/ml against fungal stain.

Thus, antifungal activity of 6 was comparable to the standard.

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